

STRATEGIC PLANNING AND ITS IMPACT ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIAN BOTTLING COMPANY, ENUGU

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Abstract: The study investigated the effects of strategic planning on organizational performance with Nigerian Bottling Company Enugu, as a case in hand; the aim is to know whether strategic planning has effect on the overall performance of the organization. The methodology that was used for the study is survey design and the target population was 180 members of staff of Nigerian Bottling Company Enugu while the sample size was 124 which were determined using Taro Yamen's formula. The result of the analysis indicate that there is relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational performance and also that lack of accountability, lack of commitment and lack of understanding of the role in the execution process are challenges in the implementation of strategic planning and therefore recommend among others that Nigerian firms should give more serious attention to strategic planning and finally, employee welfare should also be given adequate attention for efficiency and effectiveness in organization.

Keywords: Strategic Planning, Organizational Performance, Nigerian Bottling Company, Business Strategy Implementation, Employee Commitment

Introduction

Strategy is designed to help firms achieve competitive advantage. In the broadest sense, competitive advantage is what allows a firm to gain an edge over its rivals. Competitive advantage enables a firm to achieve high performance over an extended period of time. Strategic planning therefore is part of the contemporary managerial tool kits not only for dealing with the inevitable uncertainty in the management environment but also, for stimulating organizational performance (Schendel, 2009).

Strategic planning is a vital instrument in an organizational setting. It is defined as the process of determining the future of overall goal or objective of a business. Planning therefore bridges the gap between where we are, and where we want to go (Adeleke, 2001). Planning can be a very difficult exercise because it requires that we consciously determine a course of action and base our decisions on hope, purpose, and knowledge on estimates. Nevertheless, the performance of any organization depends on the extent to which the use of strategic planning is put in place in order to accomplish the set objectives and mission statement of that organization (Adeleke, 2001).

Strategic planning focuses upon long range objectives and short-term priorities. A properly structured strategic plan enables management to comprehend the relationship of goals, objectives and action attainment Dawson (2006).

In majority of organization in Nigeria, planning is the most important management tool for performance and for organizations to perform well, resources must be well utilized and customers well served. To achieve such ends, all of an organization's human and materials resources must be well utilized in the right way and the right time to create high quality products at minimal cost.

Productivity is a summary measure of the quantity and quality of work performance, with resources utilization taken into account. It can be measured at the individual, group, or organizations level, Productivity may be expressed as success into dimensions of organizations performance, effectiveness and efficiency (Dawson, 2006).

Planning on the other hand, is regarded as the most basic of all the management functions. It involves the selecting from among alternative future course of action for the organization as a whole and every department or section within it. Furthermore, it requires selecting organizational objectives and departmental goals, determines and provides a rational approach to pre-selected objectives. It strongly implies managerial innovation and the ability to create something (Dawson, 2006).

Statement of Problems

In view of the many challenges that business organizations are exposed to, it is imperative for them, both profit and nonprofit organizations, to anticipate challenges, identify their strengths to meet anticipated challenges and take control of available opportunities to obtain maximum productivity.

Unfortunately, in most organizations, strategic plans are not carried out and implemented properly. Some organizations do not attach any importance to strategic planning and therefore do not have strategic plans for their organizations. This could be borne out of lack of appreciation and knowledge of the relevance of strategic planning to organizational growth.

Despite the fact that strategic planning has brought far reaching revolution which has tremendously transformed most business landscape, it is still plagued with some constraints in so many organizations. Some of these constraints include wrong application of strategic planning, unethical attitude, poor organizational structure and Non conformity of the rules and standards by the workers of the company towards actualization of the strategic goals. In an attempt to address this unfortunate development, there is the need to critically assess the relevance of strategic planning on organizational productivity to enable management appreciate its worth in gaining competitive advantage at the market place.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to ascertain the effect of strategic planning on organizational performance.

The specific objectives are

- i. To determine the relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational performance in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu
- ii. To examine if effective strategic planning enhances employees' performance in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu
- iii. Examine the challenges in the implementation of strategic planning in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu

Research Questions

- i. Is there any relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational productivity in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu?
- ii. Does effective strategic planning enhance employees' performance in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu?
- iii. What are the challenges in the implementation of strategic planning in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu?

Review of Related Literature

Concept of Planning

Planning is one of the fundamentals of life especially modern life. Planning is one of the management functions which is the process of setting goals and objectives in an organization and determining how to achieve such goals and objectives (Alaka, Tijani & Abass, 2011).

Hofer & Schendel (2003) asserts that it is an anticipatory decision making process for effective performance. Planning occupies a central position in management and obviously, it is difficult to talk about management without planning. However, a plan is concrete in nature, does not allow deviation, and is not flexible, but strategic planning is very flexible and open for adaptation and change when needed as a result of real-time strategic issues. Real time management issues translate to surpriseful changes arising from many sources while implementing strategic plan. The function of planning involves evolving mission statement and objectives as well as designing the actions to achieve them (Oyedijo, 2004). Other important management functions include organizing, coordinating, directing, and controlling.

Types of Planning

Long-range planning- Involves identifying those activities to be performed over an extended period of time. Long range plan may extend for several decades. Long range planning is different from strategic planning, which is primarily concerned with how the organization will position itself among competing firms in a market. Long-range planning identifies the activities to be performed that will lead to the accomplishment of official goals. One important feature of a long-range plan is necessarily different from shorter planning horizons in a plan covering 20 years (Oyedijo, 2004).

Intermediate Planning- Identifies activities to be carried out over a period of five years at the middle levels of the organization. Intermediate planning is critical in most cases to the success. Intermediate planning is focused more on the activities that have to be carried out with a planning horizon that contains fewer uncertainties (Oyedijo, 2004).

Short-range Planning: Developing plans for implementation within a planning horizon of less than one year is often referred to as short-range planning. Short-range plans may specify activities to be carried out that will achieve certain production levels each week. While short-range plans are necessary for most organizations, they can have set backs. Often managers become so focused on short-range plans. Ultimately, this can lead to failure in the accomplishment of organizational goals (Oyedijo, 2004).

Concept of Strategy

Strategy is the direction and scope of the organization over the long term which deliver a competitive edge for the firm amidst an ever changing business environment. Effective strategy configures a firm's resources and core competencies so as to adequately meet the firm's goals and objectives. Strategy creates a culture in the firm in which the firm only focuses on the value adding priorities in its mission and vision (Johnson, Scholes, and Whittington, 2008).

Competitive strategy is aimed at creating a goodness of fit between the firm's internal resources capabilities and the environmental challenges faced (Aosa, 2002). At the core of strategic management is the concept of strategy (Ansoff and McDonnell, 2007). There is no universally accepted definition of strategy (Mintzberg, Guinn and Ghoshal, 2003). In the military context, strategy has been associated with how war is conducted. In general application, strategy has been taken as a plan for attaining a goal. Mintzberg and Quinn (1991) have defined strategy using five dimensions. This dimensions' view strategy as a plan, a ploy, a pattern, a position and a perspective. The most basic definition of strategy regards strategy as the long term direction of an organization (Johnson and Scholes, 2004).

Grant (2003) asserts that business managers exhibiting substantial autonomy and flexibility in strategy making reap successful performance. The structure of the planning systems allows corporate management establishes constraints and guidelines in the form of vision and mission statements, corporate initiatives and performance expectations.

Concept of Strategic Planning

Steiner (2009) defines strategic planning as the systematic and more or less formalized effort of a company to establish basic company purposes, objectives, policies and strategies. It involves the development of detailed plans to implement policies and strategies to achieve objectives and basic company purposes.

Strategic planning is an organization's process of defining its strategy, or direction, and making decisions on allocating its resources to pursue this strategy including its capital and people (Adeleke *et al*, 2008).

These plethora's of definitions are complementary in the sense they express and sometimes confuse with planning itself. Is strategic planning synonymous with planning? We will rely on the insights drawn earlier in the definitions of planning, long term planning and consequently strategic planning in this study, to propose a better description of strategic planning as a means designed to pursue well-articulated goals of an organization with reliable alternative means to ensure the attainment of these articulated goals. What makes strategic planning different from ordinary planning include the following:

- i. Strategic planning is aimed at capturing, occupying and maintaining competitive positions to have edge over contemporaries while planning is aimed at undergoing normal flow of business activities.
- ii. Strategic planning is intended to have long run effects on the firm while planning may only have short run effects.
- iii. Strategic planning due to its affiliation with the military and sensitive issues creates actions and alternative actions (intended to responds to possible future changes) towards the goal of the organization while planning may not because there is always time to change the one and only plans without much damage.
- iv. All strategic plans are long term but not all long term plans are strategic plan. Some long term plans are not properly planned.
- v. Strategic planning is environment conscious while plan/long term plan is not. Strategic planning assumes that an organization must be responsive to a dynamic, changing environment.
- vi. A plan is concrete in nature, doesn't allow deviation, and not flexible, but strategic planning is very flexible and open for adaptation and change when needed as a result of real-time strategic issues.

Grant (2003) notes that empirical research is strategic planning systems have focused on two areas: the impact of strategic planning on firm performance and the role of strategic planning in strategic decision making. The latter area of research explored the organizational process of strategy formulation.

Berry (2004) defines strategic planning as a management process that combines four basic features; a clear statement of the organization's mission; the identification of the agency's external constituencies or stakeholders, and the delineation of the agency's strategic goals and objectives, typically in a 3-5 years plan; and the development of strategies to achieve them.

Factors Influencing Strategic Planning

There are many factors listed in the literature that influence strategic planning process. Environmental uncertainties hampers the development of long range plans; scarce resource strategic planning should be aligned to use scarce resources effectively; legal forces legislative changes introduce new dynamics in an industry thus affecting strategic planning; size and complexity of an organization – as size and complexity of an organization increases, so does the degree of formulating of planning activities; the extent of involvement in operating issues compromises the attention paid to management functions; the implementation gap – this is the inability of the top management and the planners to effectively communicate with the planners; the lifecycle of the organization – as organizations move through different phases, the competitive environment changes and influences the way they plan and execute strategy (Thompson, *et al*, 2007). Organizations need to plan for a number of reasons. These are; to reorient the organization or institution to the needs of the community; another serious consideration is that when people plan for expansion, a certain level of minimum standard must be observed. This will guarantee a certain level of minimum quality performance. Effective strategic planning initiatives make organizations more responsive and viable instrument for socio-economic development (Robinson and Pearce, 2003). Strategic planning is a continuous process that requires constant feedback about how the current strategies are working.

Challenges of strategic planning

There are some challenges in the implementation of strategic plans which restrained effectiveness of plans. Some of these challenges are:

Lack of accountability: No plan could be effectively implemented without reviewing progress of plans regularly. Plans could not be effective without proper monitoring system. When plans are not reviewed regularly then no corrective erasures could be made and as a result plans become irrelevant to the business operations (Marx, 2004).

Lack of commitment: Lack of commitment from management in the planning process is a main and root cause of all the obstacles in effective strategic planning. When management didn't take interest in formulation and implementation of strategy then all other hurdles create. Limited accountability, strict time limits on reviews and a strict scheduled for reviewing the plans all are the obstacles just due to lack of management commitment (Marx, 2004).

Inadequate instructions to employees: Managers usually fail to adequately anticipate the required training and instructions for the employees in order to equip their employees with the skills required for the implementation of strategy. Sometime planners didn't link employee's performance with the reward system during implementation phase. There is generally a mismatch between anticipated times for implementation which is considered during strategy formulation stage and the actually time needed to takes it to complete the execution of the strategy (Al-Ghamdi, 2008).

Power & Influence: The way in which organizations usually conduct its businesses provide some people in organization with power and influence. Any strategy that could result in a change within organization and which might disrupt their power and influence is generally opposed. People have their interest with status co, sometime such change is also threaten to top management because unfamiliarity with new rolls, analytical techniques. When organizations are divided in different business units then some of top managers feel that their control over firm and their influence will be diminish that's why they create hurdles in implementation of strategic plans (Marx, 2004).

Culture: In order to successfully implement a strategy we have to change our culture. As in organizations usually culture is no support the risk taking, on the other hand for success entrepreneurial ship and risk taking is very much necessary. We need a culture which support risk

taking, business cannot avoid risk by saying that we will not address it. If culture is not supporting then implementation will be restricted only toward generic strategies instead of a specific strategy required by firm to cope with challenges (Jones and Goldberg, 1999).

Organizational Structure/Design and Organizational Performance

Nnabuife (2009) defines organizational performance as setting up a structure or mending an already existing one to suit the organizational environment and the demands of technology. Organizational structure also referred to as organizational design provides a solid foundation for company operations by laying out the physical grouping of employees and the managerial hierarchies within an organization. Organizational design essentially provides a guide for the way in which work is to be completed within the organization by determining how task, decision and information flow into the company. Organizational design translates the goals and desires of business leaders into actual, tangible plans. Organizational design can serve as an element of a strategic plan to accomplish specific objectives since organizational structure influences the way in which work flows in a company. Therefore, different design can help or hinder different strategic objectives and also can aid or hinder employees in their role. Structure can dictate the means by which strategies are formed, for instance, Companies with good structure, on the other hand, often involve a range of employees in strategy sessions. For organization to deliver its plan, the strategy and the structure must be woven together seamlessly. They involve combining flexible decision making, and sharing the best ideas across the organization, with appropriate levels of management and control from the centre. A company's organizational structure must support its strategy. For instance, in a case where downsizing is the strategy, organizational design involves figuring out which positions or department to trim. When introducing a new line of business, organizational design means figuring out who is responsible for the new business, how many positions should be opened and where in the reporting structure in the new line belongs. Normally businesses draft these changes into a formal organizational chart so that everyone involved can clearly understand the changes and how the business should operate. Employees at all levels of company must be empowered to effectively complete the task necessary to achieve organizational objectives.

There is hardly any organization that does not have profit and growth as its main objectives. The growth of a firm is principally measured on the percentage of market share captured and client served. By deciding how to approach the markets and Customers, employees are placed into different strategic positions to execute the strategies established by the organization hence organizational structure is actually integral of strategic planning. However empirical evidence by Williams (1997) confirms a positive relationship between organizational structure and strategic planning while Weir (1995) in his effort to establish the relationship between organizational structure and corporate performance concludes that firms that adopted appropriate structure yield higher profits than those that do not.

Employee Welfare and Organizational Performance

The essence of strategic planning is for attainment of organizational objectives. Every organization exists to achieve an objective. The attainment of these objectives makes the existence of every organization formal and as well assures its performance, sustainability and survival. Gloss (1980) in Nwosu (2014) maintains that organization that does not have survival as its primary objectives or goal must have a rethink if it must continue to exist. However, for organizations to survive through attainment of its objectives, employees must play an indispensable role. Organizations have life and it is the employees in the organization that breathe life into organizations, therefore, every organization must Endeavour to take the welfare of its human resources very serious for assurance of effective strategic planning. Employee welfare is an indispensable factor of strategic planning as all tenets of strategic planning (formulation, implementation, evaluation and control) must be executed only by capable, qualified and

loyal workforce. Priti (2009) argues that the role of welfare activities is to promote economic development by increasing efficiency and productivity with the underlying principle of making workers give their loyal services ungrudgingly in genuine spirit of co-operation and the general well-being of the employee. Despite this, Mwiti (2007) points out that naturally welfare services may not directly relate to an employee's job but the presence or absence of the services is notable through employee performance, attitude, high or low labour turnover. It is argued that, welfare services can be used to secure the labour force by providing proper human conditions of work and living through minimizing the hazardous effect on the life of the workers and their family members (Manzini & Gwandure, 2011).

Research Method

Research Design

Survey research design was adopted for this study. Descriptive survey research design is the systematic collection of data in standardized form from an identifiable population or representative (Oso & Onen, 2009). This design was adopted for this study because it intensively described and analyzed the role of strategic planning on performance brewing firms in Nigeria. The target population of the study is 180 members of staff of Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu

Instrument of Data Collection

Four (4) point Likert scale questionnaire whose content comprise a closed-ended questions was used to collect data. Questionnaires were administered to the staff of Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: The mean and standard deviations of the respondents „response on the Relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational performance in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu

	N	TOTAL	MEAN	SD	DECISION
Through Strategic Planning, organizational Goal and Objectives can be achieved.	124	450	3.63	0.45	Accept
Strategic planning can ensure better decision making in the organization	124	434	3.50	0.50	Accept
Effective organizational communication can be derived through strategic planning	124	455	3.67	0.47	Accept
Effective human resource management can be achieved through strategic planning	124	422	3.40	0.49	Accept
Strategic planning ensures organizational co-operation towards a common goal	124	471	3.80	0.40	Accept
Organizational Growth can be achieved through strategic planning	124	412	3.32	0.47	Accept
			G. Mean		
			3.55		

Source: Field work, 2017

The data in table 1 shows that the respondents accepted items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 with respective mean score of 3.63, 3.50, 3.67, 3.40, 3.80 and 3.32 and standard deviation scores of 0.45, 0.50, 0.47, 0.49, 0.40 and 0.47. The items were accepted because the mean scores were up to and above 2.50 mean cut-off mark. It implies that there is a relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational performance.

Table 2: The mean and standard deviations of the respondents „response on the effective strategic planning enhances employee’s performance in Nigeria bottling Company

	N	TOTAL	MEAN	SD	DECISION
Strategic planning can help employee meet their targets easily	124	383	3.09	0.26	Accept
Adequate Training and Development of Staff on effective Planning can improved employees Performance	124	476	3.84	0.03	Accept
Strategic planning can lead to employee satisfaction and hence better performance	124	418	3.37	0.04	Accept
Strategic Planning programmes are usually relevant to employee	124	496	4.00	0.00	Accept

Performance.

11 Firms that have effectively embraced strategic planning, record better employee

performance compared to those that have not **Grand Mean 3.51**

Source: Field work, 2017

The data in table 2 shows that the respondents accepted items 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 with respective mean score of 3.09, 3.84, 3.37, 4.00 and 3.27 and standard deviation scores of 0.45, 0.50, 0.47, 0.49, 0.40 and 0.47. The items were accepted because the mean scores were up to and above 2.50 mean cut-off mark. It implies that there is a relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational performance.

Table 3: The mean and standard deviations of the respondents „response on the challenges in the implementation of strategic planning in Nigeria bottling Company?

	N	TOTAL	MEAN	SD	DECISION
12 Lack of accountability	124	496	4.00	0.00	Accept
13 Lack of commitment	124	489	3.94	0.02	Accept
14 Inadequate instructions to employees	124470		3.79	0.04	Accept
Information system used for implementation is inadequate	124489		3.94	0.02	Accept
Lack of understanding of the role in the execution process	124 in the483		3.90	0.03	Accept
			Grand Mean		
			3.91		

Source: Field work, 2017

The data in table 4.3 shows that the respondents accepted items 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 with respective mean score of 4.00, 3.94, 3.79, 3.94 and 3.90 and standard deviation scores of 0.00, 0.02, 0.04, 0.49, 0.02 and 0.03. The items were accepted because the mean scores were up to and above 2.50 mean cut-off mark. It implies that lack of accountability, lack of commitment, inadequate instructions to employees, information system used for implementation is inadequate and lack of understanding of the role in the execution process are challenges in the implementation of strategic planning.

Discussion of Findings

The question for objective 1 was designed to know if there any relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational productivity in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu using research question 1.

With descriptive statistics, the mean responses for variables from research questions 1 was above 2.5 at 4 point Likert scale which confirm that respondents agreed to issues raised in the questionnaire. To test the hypothesis, a t- test was conducted at 5% level of significance. The result from t-test attests that the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 and the null hypothesis was rejected. We hereby agree that there is relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational productivity in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu. This result is line with the result of research by Al-Shammari *et al* (2007) studied the relationship between strategic planning and firm performance in a non- western emergent market and it was found that firms engaging in strategic planning have better financial and performance than firms that are not implementing this important practice.

The question for objective 2 was designed to determine if there is significant relationship between strategic planning and employee’s performance using research question 2.

With descriptive statistics, the mean responses for variables from research questions 1 was above 2.5 at 4 point Likert scale which confirm that respondents agreed to issues raised in the questionnaire. To test the hypothesis, a t- test was conducted at 5% level of significance. The result from t-test attests that the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 and the null hypothesis was rejected. We hereby agree that there relationship between effective strategic planning and employee’s performance in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu. This result is line with the result of research by Kraus *et al.*, (2006) opined that

strategic planning is one of the dimensions, believes to be able to increase employee's performance, efficiency and effectiveness of organization planning).

Summary of Findings

The following findings were made from the study.

1. Majority of the respondents were male
2. Majority of the respondents were between the age 20-30years
3. The study also revealed that majority of the respondents were married
4. It was also evident that majority of the respondents had HND/B.SC qualification
5. Also majority of the respondents have been in service for 0-5years
6. There is relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational productivity in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu
7. There is relationship between effective strategic planning and employees' performance in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu.
8. The study also revealed that lack of accountability, lack of commitment, inadequate instructions to employees, information system used for implementation is inadequate and lack of understanding of the role in the execution process were challenges in the implementation of strategic planning in Nigeria Bottling Company Enugu.

Conclusion

Based on the literature review and above discussion on effect of strategic planning and organizational performance, it can be concluded that, strategic planning has important contributions in order to achieve a better organizations and employees' performance. Therefore, the relationship of each dimensions of strategic planning was tested toward performance of the organization. It is hoped that the findings of this study will be able to help the organization to understand how the strategic planning can help to make better decision in the future.

Recommendations

In the light of above findings, some pertinent recommendations were made. These recommendations are geared towards assurance of organizational and employees' performance, growth through effective strategic planning. This study recommends the following:

1. That Nigeria firms should give more serious attention to strategic planning, separate other types of planning from strategic planning, endeavor to choose appropriate strategies that matches for every strategic plans and as well adopt and effectively implement the full tenets of strategic planning.
2. Employee welfare is an indispensable factor of strategic planning as all tenets of strategic planning (formulation, implementation, evaluation and control) must be executed through its human capital, therefore every organization must endeavor to take the welfare of its human resources very serious for assurance of effective strategic planning. In other words, for organizations to survive through attainment of its objectives, employees must play an indispensable role.
3. Those Organizations should endeavor to capture more or at least maintain its market especially through merger and acquisition because larger market share lead to high turnover, higher profit and better performance.
4. Technological changes affect product quality and price therefore organizations should endeavor to rapidly respond to technological changes.

Organizations should endeavor to adopt appropriate training because appropriate training provides a solid foundation for employees' performance.

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